

INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH OF MWNT / EPOXY COMPOSITES AND COMPARISON WITH MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted much attention because of their unique structure and remarkable mechanical, electrical, thermal and chemical properties. In particular, it has been believed that CNTs are ideal fillers for polymers to enhance their mechanical properties. Numerous efforts have been devoted to the application of SWNTs and MWNTs to polymers for the last decade [1]. However, it has been revealed that mechanical properties of CNT-dispersed polymers are generally inferior to the theoretical values.

It has been understood that the mechanical properties of CNT-dispersed polymer matrix composites are dominated mainly by dispersion, alignment, and interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between CNT and the polymer. In particular, weak IFSS between CNT and polymer is thought to be a critical problem [2]. From this perspective, many analytical studies have been conducted. However, it is not hard to anticipate that traditional methods are difficult to apply for measurements because of the extremely small size of CNTs, so direct comparison with analytical results and experimental results was not conducted.

From this point of view, we proposed simple and easy method to evaluate the IFSS of CNT-dispersed thermoplastic polymer composites (so-called Nano-pullout system [3]) for obtaining reasonable experimental results.

In this study, the interfacial shear strengths of MWNT/ epoxy composites were evaluated using a nano-pullout method. Furthermore numerical simulations based on molecular dynamics (MD) were

carried out. The experimental results were compared with the numerical results.

2 Experimental procedures and MD calculation method

2.1 Materials

MWNTs used in this study were vapor grown carbon nanofiber (VGCFTM) obtained from Showa Denko Inc. (Tokyo, Japan). The diameter was 100–150 nm; their length was about several micrometers. Bisphenol-F-type epoxy (Epicote 807, Mitsubishi Chemicals) and aromatic diamine hardener (Epomate B002) were mixed at the weight ratio of 100:55.

We evaluated two kinds of samples; i.e. sample A and sample-B. Sample A is 1 wt% VGCF/epoxy composites after tensile testing, whereas sample B is 3 wt% VGCF/epoxy composites before tensile testing. It was anticipated that the sample A includes much more interfacial damages because of tensile loading. Fig.1 shows a transmission electron microscope (TEM) image of Sample-B. Many MWNTs are visible at the specimen edge.

2.2 Nano-pullout testing

The test procedure is presented schematically in Fig.2. An individual MWNT is pulled out from a MWNT/Epoxy composite film within an FE-SEM (JSM-6300F; JEOL, Japan) that a nano-pullout testing system is installed in. A manipulation system for nano-pullout testing which is shown in Fig.3 consists of X, Y, Z stages driven by supersonic linear motors (travel 5 mm, resolution 1 μ m; Technohands Co. Ltd., Japan) for coarse positioning, and X and Z

piezoelectric actuators (travel 17 μm , resolution 1 nm; Fuji Ceramics Corp., Japan) for fine positioning. An AFM cantilever (ZEILR-20; Nanoworld AG, Switzerland) was fixed on an X piezoelectric actuator to measure the applied force, whereas a specimen was mounted on the opposite side Z supersonic linear motor.

A MWNT was bonded at the tip of an AFM cantilever using electron beam induced deposition (EBID) method presented as shown in Fig. 4. Tensile load is applied to X direction using an X piezoelectric actuator, and a MWNT is pulled out from the composite.

The pullout load is determined using the displacement of an AFM cantilever tip. The average interfacial shear strength is calculated using a simple force balance under the assumption of uniform shear stress distribution along a CNT surface, as average.

$$\tau_{\text{average}} = \frac{F_{\text{pullout}}}{\pi D_{\text{CNT}} L_{\text{emb}}} \quad (1)$$

where F_{pullout} is the pull-out force at interfacial rupture, D_{CNT} is the outer diameter, and L_{emb} is the embedded length of the CNTs. Actually, F_{pullout} is estimated as

$$F_{\text{pullout}} = k\Delta x \quad (2)$$

where k is a spring constant of the cantilever, and Δx is a relative displacement of the cantilever tip after testing. The diameter of each CNT was measured using an SEM observation. Furthermore, Δx was evaluated from SEM images, i.e., the position of the cantilever before and after pullout test was compared directly (Fig. 4). The spring constant of the cantilever used in this experiment was about 2.2 ~ 2.6 N/m.

2.3 Molecular Dynamics calculations

Although MWNTs were used for the composites, CNT pullout simulations are performed for single-wall CNT (SWNT) / epoxy composite using MD because of the limitation in the capability of our computer. The MD models are shown in Fig.5 (a) and (b). The numbers of atoms are 17396. A fully embedded, 6.5 \AA radius, 80 \AA long SWNT (896 atoms) is being ‘‘pulled’’ out of the 55 epoxy polymers (polymerization 4,300 atoms on each polymer) by moving SWNT at a constant displacement rate of 0.024 \AA /fs. For the interaction between SWNT and Epoxy, the *Lennard-Jones* 12-6 type potential was applied;

$$\Phi = \left(\frac{R_0}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{R_0}{r}\right)^6 \quad (4)$$

The number of calculation steps was 20,000, and the time interval of each step was 0.25 fs. Calculation temperature was 298 K, which is same as experiments and the Coulomb forces on each atoms is also taken into account.

3 Results and discussion

The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between MWNT and epoxy are summarized in Table.1 for sample- A, and Table.2 for sample-B. The IFSS is in the range of 3–10 MPa (average 5.1 MPa, standard deviation (SD) 2.7 MPa) in case of the sample A, and 9–30 MPa (average 19.6 MPa, SD 8.5 MPa) in case of the sample B, which is nearly same as those of MWNT/PEEK composites [3]. Sample B exhibits higher IFSS than sample A. These results suggest that the IFSS between CNT and epoxy is relatively weak compared with existing materials [4].

The maximum tensile stress of CNT, which appears outside of composite, is calculated as shown below:

$$\sigma_{\text{max}} = \frac{F_{\text{pullout}}}{\pi(D_{\text{CNT}}/2)^2} \quad (6)$$

The tensile stress of CNT is estimated as around 0.5 ~ 1 GPa (sample A) and 1 ~ 3 GPa (sample B). Tensile stress of CNT in sample B is estimated to be higher than that of sample A. These values are much smaller than the typical tensile strengths of CNT[5], which suggests that CNT breakage did not occur inside and outside of composite in these experiments.

TEM image portraying a MWNT of sample-B is shown in Fig.1. This implies that the surface of CNT is flat and matrix polymer (epoxy) is not obviously observed on the CNT surface. Therefore, it seems that *van der Waals* forces play an important role in IFSS between CNT and epoxy.

Fig.6 shows a MD model at 4 ps when a SWNT is completely pulled out from epoxy. Compared with the location of each atom before the calculation, the epoxy atoms around a SWNT slightly move upward. This is due to *van der Waals* forces between SWNT surface and the adjacent epoxy atoms. The force corresponded to interfacial shear stress between CNT and epoxy in a macroscopic phenomenon.

Fig.7 shows the potential energy trace of whole MD model as a function of the time of the simulation. The potential energy gradually reduces while the simulation.

Fig.8 shows the potential energy trace of SWNT in Fig.7. The potential energy of CNT increases during SWNT pullout proceeds. A SWNT is completely embedded in epoxy at the start of the simulation, and the exposed surface area of the SWNT increases gradually as simulation proceeds. The potential energy change ($E_{pullout}$ in Fig.8) is assumed to be the energy used for CNT pullout. Therefore the IFSS can be calculated from the following equation [6]:

$$\tau_{average} = \frac{E_{pullout}}{\pi D_{CNT} L_{emb}^2} \quad (5)$$

The estimated IFSS was 3.8 MPa. This value is closed to the experimental results of sample A, however lower than that of sample B. These results indicate the possibility that *van der Waals* force is insufficient for explaining the IFSS between CNT and polymer.

4 Conclusions

Interfacial shear strengths (IFSS) of MWNT/epoxy composites were directly measured using a nano-pullout method. The measured IFSS is 5.1 MPa for the specimens after tensile fracture, and 19.6 MPa for the specimens without tensile loading. This suggests that the interface is damaged by tensile loading.

The MD simulation results almost agreed with the experimental results of the specimens after tensile fracture. This implies that the other bonding force should be taken into account for pristine MWNT/Epoxy composites in addition to *Van der Waals* forces.

References

- [1] ET. Thostenson, Z. Ren T-W. Chou “Advances in the science and technology of carbon nanotubes and their composites: a review” *Compos Sci Technol*, NO. 61, pp 1899-1912, 2001.
- [2] LS. Schadler, SC. Giannaris, PM.Ajayan “Load transfer in carbon nanotube epoxy composites” *Appl Phys Lett*, NO.73, pp3824-3842, 1998.
- [3] T. Tsuda, T. Ogasawara, F. Deng, N. Takeda “Direct measurements of interfacial shear strength of multi-walled

carbon nanotube / PEEK composite using a nano-pullout method” *Compos Sci Technol*, 2011, in press.

[4] D. Hull and T. W. Clyne “An Introduction to Composite Materials” Cambridge Univ. Press,1996.

[5] Peng B, Locascio M, Zapol P, Li S, Mielke SL, Schatz GC, et al. “Measurements of near-ultimate strength for multiwalled carbon nanotubes and irradiation induced crosslinking improvements” *Nature nanotech*, No.3, pp626-31, 2008.

[6] K. Liao, S. Li “Interfacial characteristics of a carbon nanotube-polystyrene composite system” *Appl Phys Lett*, No.79, pp4225-4227, 2001.

Fig.1 TEM image of Vapor Grown Carbon Fiber (VGCF).

Fig.2 Schematic drawing illustrating the procedure of nano-pullout testing.

Fig.3. Manipulation system for the nano-pullout testing. Three supersonic linear motors and two piezoelectric actuators are used for the positioning and pull-out moving.

Fig.4. SEM image of superimpose display of digital images before and after pull-out testing results.

Fig.5. Molecular Dynamics model (From (a) top view and (b) side view). In Fig. 5 (b), CNT is completely embedded in epoxy resin.

Fig.6 after complete pullout of MD model.

Fig.7 Energy trace of a whole MD model.

Fig.8 Energy trace of a SWNT.

Table.1 Nano-pullout results (for sample A)

Experiment No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Pulled out CNT length, L_{emb} (μm)	5.8	10	4.4	5.6	5.1	3.0	9.6
CNT diameter, D_{CNT} (nm)	180	210	160	230	210	150	200
Cantilever displacement at pull-out (μm)	5.3	11	8.9	13	4.4	3.4	6.8
Pull-out force, $F_{pullout}$ (μN)	13	27	22	28	9.7	7.4	15
Interfacial shear strength, IFSS (MPa)	4.1	4.0	10	6.9	2.9	5.1	2.5
Tensile stress (GPa)	0.54	0.76	1.2	0.67	0.28	0.40	0.50
Spring constant of cantilever (N/m)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2

Table.2 Nano-pullout results (for sample B)

Experiment No.	1	2	3	4	5
Pulled out CNT length, L_{emb} (μm)	1.5	5.3	2.7	5.7	3.3
CNT diameter, D_{CNT} (nm)	110	130	140	130	100
Cantilever displacement at pull-out (μm)	6.5	16	13	9.4	6.1
Pull-out force, $F_{pullout}$ (μN)	15	37	31	21	16
Interfacial shear strength, IFSS (MPa)	30	18	26	8.9	15
Tensile stress (GPa)	1.6	3.2	2.0	1.6	1.9
Spring constant of cantilever (N/m)	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.2	2.6